

Mass Media: An Integral Component of Holistic Social Development

Emanuel Dobrin, PhD (cand.)

University of Bucharest, Romania
edobrin75@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: In the contemporary age, mass media—the solitary technical means for the delivery of information to the people—developed not only an exerting mobilizing power, but also impacted the development of human personality. In this day and age, dominated by the mass media, the human being is conditioned by the mass media and has become subject to the continuing pressures of the information propagated by it. In this context, invariably, the human personality is being affected (even redefined), as it develops new positive or negative impulses; depending on the information it is being exposed to.

KEY WORDS: media, information, human personality, technology, development, influence.

In the present society, addicted to the information technology, the role of the mass media is more pronounced in almost all areas. Information has become an indispensable source within the educational, socio-economic process and the mass media the main way of propagating it. But, beyond the mere role of information, through mass media judgments are being issued, opinions are being outlined, ideas are born and maybe most importantly, the personality of the individual is being redefined.

The present paper, presents in short, mass media as part of the holistic social development. This aspect is being explained by

highlighting of the three dimensions: the role of media in the society, the impact of mass media on the human being and its effects on human personality. Without claiming perfection, the paper is part of a necessary step in order to understand the way in which the human personality is redefined through mass media.

The contact between a human being and its environment is possible through the senses with which the human being is endowed, visual, auditory, olfactory, gustative and tactile. Of these, the visual sense is the gate through which, the most images and information enter the human receivers. In this whole process, the mass media is being imposed as a social intermediation function between the human being and the environmental conditions, facilitating the accumulation of information from the environment.

The relationship between the mass media and the human personality develops as a cause-effect dualism, generating global consequences, precise influences and predetermined attitudes. Therefore, the mass media has an informational role, but also an effect due to the fact that through the transmitted information the thinking and the behavior of the human being is being influenced.

The role of the mass media in society

Social remodeling through mass media has become a phenomenon which tends toward globalization, in spite of the barriers imposed by certain states in the East, Asia, or Africa.

In the attempt to understand, master and judge the surrounding world, more and more groups and collectivities depend on the mass media, or implement technological information systems. Thus a stream of messages is being created on the basis of which decisions and investments are being made and new ways of socio-economic development are being drawn.

This continuous flow of messages, observes Coman, envelopes almost entirely individuals and society, removing time for reflection, review and critical analysis of the offered versions.¹

The ethical and moral extent, in which this flow of information will be governed, can provide a positive development of the society

and implicitly of the human being. The mass media mediates many relations between the state and the public and as Coman said, in the modern world, the mass media has become “the fourth power in the state,” a sort of gravitational center in relation to which all other segments of the society position.²

Thus the mass media becomes a sort of an interface between the two extremes, the state and the public, offering both parties the opportunity of virtual interaction. The mass media has not only become a channel through which information is being transmitted, but also a source of information, through which it generates changes in the attitudes of the public, observes McQuail.³

Thus, from the perspective of forming of public opinion, the mass media complex is the main link, and in this social and economic perimeter this complex becomes increasingly important, the more since the Tech society proposes new dimensions of development. The issue of mass media, as a source of information, is given by the nature of the information which it propagates. But, also in this case things are divided between those who hold the information and those receiving the information, the holder of the information becoming a key element in this process of formatting the human structure.

The mass media, can provide the capture and broadcasting of information, and through this it can arouse a person’s curiosity, it can generate new interests, it can help develop training systems, it can widen the knowledge horizon in a certain area, it can provide resources for social integration, it can help develop someone’s taste for art or culture, it can shape an individual in lots of possible ways. On the other hand, all this remodeling conceived in a perverted way, may represent deception, degradation and compromise. The background problematic is not provided by the positive development or the compromise, which the mass media has on a person, but by the fact that the hidden purpose is to influence a group as large as possible, to create a new opinion, as stated by Dobrescu.⁴

In general, opinions change according to the information individuals or groups hold, and new information triggers a reorder process. Of course, each individual or group welcomes information in a certain manner, receives it in a specific way, evaluates and interprets

it differently, but the link between information and opinion is beyond any doubt a fact in which lies the overwhelming importance of the media in forming the orientation of the public opinion. About the information, one positive aspect can be highlighted related to the quality of information. When the information is precise, accurate and well formulated, automatically limits for its interpretation appear, and the answer can only be in terms of “yes” or “no”. In this case, the information can be accepted or rejected, without being open to comments. When, on the contrary, the information transmitted is vague, insufficiently defined, the field of interpretation becomes extremely wide, and the interpretation itself is made in the sense of closeness to the attitude and the interests of the one who initiated the approach.

These are just a few ways through which mass media can contribute to a holistic development of a society, without forgetting however, that the implications of mass media are not limited to those listed.

The effects of mass media in society

In Romania, as in many other countries, mass media is a power, and from all mass media means, television has the highest impact. As a device, the TV is an invention of the human mind, which in itself is not harmful, but the way in which it is being used, especially in the last 15 years, has turned it into a veritable source of manipulation.

The national and cultural factors, as well as the social and economic stratification affect the consumption of the mass media messages, and the dependency on the social system in which a particular individual lives is huge. Sometimes people are constrained to choose what they are given, which goes over all the barriers of individual control.

The daily experiences, notes Dragan, prove the dependency on mass media messages.⁵

For example, people choose a certain way of dressing under the influence of the weather forecast, shop on the basis of an advertisement, go to a movie promoted by the television and redefine

pleasures depending on what the television shows as part of the alleged social development. All these aspects highlight a society strongly affected by the messages and information from the mass media and at disposal of its ordered compliance.

Even more than these personal views, Petcu observes, that even the political candidates and the political parties are constantly concerned in finding ways by which they can communicate virtually with the electorate, so that they would win votes.⁶ From this fact results that the one that is the owner of the mass media, is also the owner of those who comply with the messages provided by the mass media.

The advertising agencies, observes Weiss, have developed an exceptional social marketing, through the knowledge of the habits, the desires and the needs, trying to create ads and messages that will bring bigger sales for a particular good.⁷ To be sure of success, specialists have created different forums on which they can post information relating to a particular product and which ensures the sale of that product.

Mass media profoundly affects society and the individual, because it is a constant presence in his life, it has a universality that no other institution has. Because of this, the analysis of the way in which the mass media affect the society, in a deliberate manner, as a result of a planned strategy or in a random way, is still one of the major concerns of researchers.

The effects of mass media can be felt in different areas of the society: D. McQuail noted that the mass media can operate on individuals, groups, institutions, the entire society, and that it can affect human personality in the cognitive dimension by changing its world view, in the emotional dimension by modifying or creating feelings or attitudes and the behavioral dimension through changes in the way in which individuals act and by social mobilization phenomenon.⁸

From another perspective, mass media may have a short-term influence, or may need a longer period of time to become operational. Also, the effects of mass media can create the desired or less desired changes. They can be the result of a controlled process, such as the press campaigns, or part of other expected or unexpected events.

The impact of the mass media on the adult population and on the children

One characteristic of mass media is that it can form the character of an individual, often erroneously by the impact it has. If from the psychological standpoint there are few resources to change the character of an adult, mass media manages this with a high success rate. If we take television as an example, due to the fact that the individual spends an exaggerated amount of time in front of the TV, his mind may be imprinted by the ideas or opinions transmitted by the program being watched. This does not occur as a result of a mental effort done by the individual, but it simply takes place via the neuronal connections which are being redefined by the received information.

Mass media may be considered responsible for the structuring of the activities and the daily routine of human beings, notes O'Reagan.⁹ The press informs daily or weekly the readers about the aggressions or abuse which occur. Of course, in many cases, the journalists pursue the sensational aspects, by publishing a series of information meant to satisfy through spicy details the taste of the public. The statistics for Romania are rather alarming.

A study titled, "Measuring the degree of violence present in the Romanian audiovisual programs" was conducted during October 13 through October 19 2008 by a team of researchers from the Center for Media Studies and New Communication Technology, and coordinated by professor Ioan Dragan, the head of the Center. The project focused on the weight, the duration and the frequency of the acts of violence broadcasted on the TV shows of 13 TV channels—TVR1, Antena 1, Antena 3, Acasa, PRO TV, Realitatea TV, Prima TV, B1 TV, OTV, Kanal D, Cartoon Network, Jetix, Minimax—that were broadcasted during news, entertainment, fictional, reality show, advertising and promo transmissions. The types of violence that were studied included: actual violence, fictional violence, as well as the verbal and physical violence, psychological, economic, sexual and social violence. The main conclusions reached by this study were that while the cartoon channels broadcast on average 20 acts of violence per one hour, mainstream and informative news broadcast an average of 14 acts of violence.

Ioan Dragan noticed that the perverse effect of these programs, although unintentional, may be the apologetic portrayal of crime and violence. Another effect was the establishment of a culture of violence, which can lead to a certain accommodation with media violence, and even with the accommodation of social violence in the life of the people. Television violence does not only affect through the dose in which it is injected into the viewer, but also through the manner in which it is understood, choreographed and interpreted.¹⁰

As a result, the children are exposed daily to some negative examples, from scenes of violence, to ads, to unhealthy products, or bad characters that come to kidnap them if they are not good. Studies show that the exposure to such messages influence the children in the first years of life, who have a tendency to imitate what they see.¹¹

For the first time, in 2006, Itsy Bitsy FM, the first radio for children, pulled an alarm signal on this subject. Under the title "Protect your child's innocence," Itsy Bitsy launched an educational campaign, which urged the parents and grandparents to be aware of the messages arriving to their children, because "Children do what they see."¹²

If for adults, observes Weiss, an advertising campaign has to work very much at the level of the psychological shaft, in order to determine by intense motivation, to consume or to buy a certain product, for children this advertising campaign will only have to present the childhood universe through happy, fun and exciting messages and images, without motivating their desire towards wanting a product.¹³ A joyful slogan, a fragment of a song, colorful images, cartoon heroes, fun and exciting actions are the means by which an advertisement draws the attention of a child and influences it.

Conclusions

Through its channels, mass media can be a "two-edged" sword. As a progress factor, its influence is reflected by raising the quality of the cultural and social life standards. As a mean of dominance and manipulation, it only provides a one-sided approach or it is reducing the public response to the great challenges of the day-to-day reality.

The perception of mass media is different from an individual to another due to the professional structure and the educational level, due to the existence and functionality of democratic institutions and the level of economic development. The greatest impact of mass media can be observed on the children, because they do not have the discernment to select the information and by this way to choose that what is best for them.

The mass media does not have a command power like the institution of the state have, but its impact on society is overwhelming, it informs by developing the critical spirit, it creates wildly held views; it launches trends and propels personalities. Used in a rational and ethical manner, mass media and the information will increase the knowledge and the development of the society, by offering major benefits. However used in a malicious manner, the mass media may constitute a destructive factor for the society.

NOTES

¹ Mihai Coman, *Mass-media în România post-comunistă* (București: Ed. Polirom, 2003), 35.

² Mihai Coman, *Introducere în sistemul mass-media* (București: Editura Polirom, 1999), 8.

³ Denis McQuail, Sven Windhal, *Modele ale comunicării pentru studiul comunicării de masă* (București Editura Școala Națională de Studii Politice și Administrative, 2001), 35.

⁴ Paul Dobrescu, Alina Bârgăoanu, *Mass-media și societatea* (București: Editura Comunicare.Ro, 2003), 114.

⁵ Ioan Drăgan, *Paradigme ale comunicării de masă* (București: Editura Șansa, 1996), 166.

⁶ Marian Petcu, *Sociologia mass-media* (Cluj-Napoca: Editura Dacia, 2002), 142.

⁷ Brigitte Weiss, *Efectele publicității: Comunicarea de piață de succes: instrumente, reguli și exemple* (București: Editura IAA, 2007), 34.

⁸ McQuail, 53.

⁹ Tom O'Reagan, *Australian Television Culture* (St. Leonards: Allen & Unwin, 1993), 65.

¹⁰ http://economie.hotnews.ro/stiri-media_publicitate-5351205-studiu-cna-desenele-animat-sunt-cele-mai-violente-emisiuni.htm, 10 jan. 2018.

¹¹ <http://www.buzzle.com/articles/negative-influences-of-media.html> (Accessed January 20, 2018).

¹² <http://www.wall-street.ro/articol/Marketing-PR/22226/Copiii-fac-cevad.html> (Accessed February 5, 2018).

¹³ Weiss, 75.